

University of Maine Student Environmental Research (UM-SER) Initiative 2025 Report

Independent Student Research in ERS 321: Problems in Earth & Climate Science, Fall 2025

Empowering Undergraduates. Advancing Climate Solutions.

December 2025

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Front Cover Illustration Credit

Cover illustration was made by ERS 321 student Gabrielle Wiley. This cover image is an illustration of the Penobscot Bay region that weaves together Maine's coastal landscape, unique landmarks, marine biodiversity, and local economy. The image blends scientific observation with visual metaphor by integrating human elements (lobster traps, buoys, and Heron Neck Lighthouse) with marine species (seals, porpoises, Atlantic salmon, lobsters, and seabirds), reflecting both ecological richness and the cultural and economic significance of Maine's coastal communities. In the deepest part of the ocean is a marine mammal acoustic recorder, like the one used by the UM-SER team, that was used to listen for the presence of baleen whales. At the heart of the graphic is a baleen whale, outlined by the ocean surface and seafloor, to highlight the significance of baleen whales to this region culturally, ecologically, and economically. By merging above- and below-water perspectives, the artwork highlights the shared dependence of wildlife, fisheries, and people on healthy coastal systems, inviting viewers to consider the need for sustainable coexistence across the region.

Acknowledgements

Financial support for *ERS 321: Problems in Earth and Climate Science* was generously provided by Nancy Arms, University of Maine Class of 1984. Without her support, this undergraduate course and the associated independent research would not have been possible. We also thank the University of Maine's Climate Change Institute and the School of Earth and Climate Sciences, particularly Drs. Paul Mayewski and Karl Kreutz, for their institutional support and leadership in enabling this course. The course itself was conceived by Dr. Paul Mayewski, whose vision and commitment to undergraduate research made its development possible.

We gratefully acknowledge the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership, especially Nicholas Keeney, for supporting our class field trip and experiential learning on Hurricane Island, as well as Tiago Bilo for his guidance and support throughout our time there. Finally, we thank Christopher Tremblay (University of Maine) and Kerry Whittaker (Maine Maritime Academy) for their expertise, collaboration, and data sharing throughout the development and execution of the course.

Citation

ERS 321: Problems in Earth and Climate Science. (2025). *University of Maine Student Environmental Research (UM-SER) Initiative 2025 Report* (Marie Zahn, Ed.). University of Maine. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18143020>

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Executive Summary

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The University of Maine Student Environmental Research (UM-SER) initiative was launched in Fall 2025 as a pilot effort to integrate undergraduate teaching, field-based research, and interdisciplinary collaboration focused on understanding and sustaining the Gulf of Maine. Implemented through the 1-credit course *ERS 321: Problems in Earth and Climate Science*, the program provided an intensive, hands-on research experience for 10 undergraduate students from diverse majors, including social work, psychology, engineering, earth science, and biology. All course objectives and outcomes were achieved in under 10 weeks and enclosed in this report are the final research projects generated by the first UM-SER cohort.

The primary objectives of ERS 321 were to introduce students to interdisciplinary environmental research and monitoring; provide hands-on training in ocean and climate field methods; develop skills in data collection, analysis, interpretation, and science communication; and foster teamwork, leadership, and problem-solving in real-world research settings. Students worked collaboratively in research teams to design and conduct oceanographic research projects relevant to the Gulf of Maine, culminating in jointly written research reports and public-facing outreach products.

A central component of the course was a field trip to Hurricane Island in September 2025, conducted in partnership with the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership and Maine Maritime Academy. During this field experience, students recovered and deployed oceanographic instrumentation and collected environmental data aboard a research vessel. In May 2025, an ocean mooring with marine mammal acoustic recorders was deployed near Hurricane Island to record the presence of baleen whales and porpoises. During the fall field trip, students successfully retrieved the ocean mooring, and they also supported the recovery and redeployment of an ocean buoy (Figure 1). The fieldwork emphasized experiential learning where they gained practical skills in instrument handling and deployment, learned how to troubleshoot technical challenges in dynamic field conditions, practiced real-time problem solving, and developed leadership and collaboration skills that will extend into their future careers.

Figure 1. Deployment of an ocean buoy aboard *M/V Sunny* near Hurricane Island.

Student research projects focused on environmental monitoring and change in the Gulf of Maine. Across the student reports, primary findings highlighted spatial and temporal variability in oceanographic conditions and phytoplankton community composition, evidence of rising sea levels, and the importance of sustained observations to understand coupled physical, ecological, and human systems. No baleen whales were detected on the acoustic recorders; however, porpoises were present every day of the recording period with increasing frequency throughout the summer. Students demonstrated the ability to synthesize field observations with existing datasets, interpret environmental signals in a regional context, and communicate uncertainty and limitations, key competencies for any scientific study.

Results from ERS 321 student projects will inform future research and benefit both the scientific community and the public. For example, student Ella Boxall presented her findings on rising sea levels to the Bar Harbor Harbor Committee, contributing to updates of local ordinances and informing future coastal development decisions. Additionally, as a final outreach outcome, students plan to submit content to the 2026 issue of *Spire: The UMaine Journal of Conservation and Sustainability*, including original artwork, poetry, photography, and written reflections that creatively communicate the scientific work conducted during the semester. These

submissions underscore the program's commitment to inclusive and innovative science communication, reaching broader audiences beyond traditional academic formats.

Overall, the Fall 2025 UM-SER Team (Figure 2) and ERS 321 course demonstrate a scalable, high-impact model for undergraduate research that integrates field science, interdisciplinary collaboration, leadership development, and public engagement, achieved within a short, intensive timeframe and with meaningful educational and scientific outcomes. In the following sections are the individual research projects completed by the students for the fall 2025 semester.

Figure 2. The 2025 ERS 321 UM-SER cohort and supporting staff from the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership during the Hurricane Island field trip. Top row (left to right): Tiago Bilo, Josie Aprea, Albert Kolodji, Marie Zahn, Kai Reed, Ella Boxall, Jamie Fogg, Cassandra, and Nathan Brame. Bottom row (left to right): Adele Jordan, Nicholas Keeney, Gabrielle Wiley-Hicks, Evelyn Runstrom, Becca Kreeger, and Erin Grabe. The vessel used for our fieldwork, *M/V Sunny*, is visible in the background.

Listening in on Penobscot Bay: Summer Presence of Baleen Whales and Porpoises

Josie Aprea, Jamie Fogg, and Gabrielle Wiley-Hicks

I. Introduction

Penobscot Bay, located in the Gulf of Maine, is a dynamic and diverse marine environment that is home to many different marine species. It's also a hotspot for human activities, including fishing and tourism. Understanding the different marine species and their presence in the area can allow us to create more efficient and conservation-oriented management strategies to maintain a healthy ecosystem. A large part of this ecosystem is the marine mammals migrating in and out of the region, specifically baleen whales and harbor porpoises (*Phocoena phocoena*). Typical baleen whale species observed in the Gulf of Maine include humpback (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), fin (*Balaenoptera physalus*), minke (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*), sei (*Balaenoptera borealis*), blue (*Balaenoptera musculus*), and North Atlantic right whales (*Eubalaena glacialis*) (Delarue, et al., 2022). However, a study done by NOAA researchers in 2020 found that in recent years marine mammal presence and distribution has changed due to alterations in their prey distribution (Davis, et al. 2020). As waters warm, prey animals, such as krill, various fish, and copepods, are migrating further poleward. This shift in marine mammal's prey migratory behavior causes a subsequent shift in the whale's migratory behavior as well (Davis, et al. 2020).

To measure marine mammal presence and abundance, researchers use passive acoustic monitoring (PAM), a noninvasive method that uses acoustic sensors, placed at depth in a marine environment, that are designed to record marine mammal vocalizations, who use their own vocalizations for inter-species communication (Halliday, et al., 2020). PAM allows researchers to assess and monitor marine mammal diversity and presence based on various factors and changes in the environment that can be acoustically captured by PAM equipment (Zitterbart et al., 2022).

The Gulf of Maine hosts a variety of marine mammals, from harbor seals to various species of delphinids and baleen whales. Whales seasonally migrate often in correlation with their prey's seasonal behaviors and feeding. The majority of baleen whale migrations into the Gulf of Maine occur during the summer months when more southern latitudes are too warm (Delarue, et al., 2022).

Penobscot Bay is popular for the fishing and tourism industries. Its beautiful landforms and biodiversity are a hot spot for human activity. For that reason, it is a high traffic region with various fishing vessels and cruise liners navigating in and out of the bay area daily. This level of

activity produces a lot of underwater noise and can cause disruptions in the marine environment, especially to acoustically driven animals, including marine mammals. Harbor porpoises use echolocation to communicate and locate prey, while baleen whales use their vocalizations primarily for the purpose of communication and mating (Reidenberg, et al., 2010).

The Penobscot River feeds directly into Penobscot Bay, transporting various minerals and nutrients into the waters allowing for dynamic biodiversity (Xue, et al. 2000 & Hurricane Island, 2020). However, with climate change and changes in marine organism distribution due to both anthropogenic and climate factors, the bay is undergoing some significant changes (NOAA, 2022). With both these climate and anthropogenic factors in mind, we hypothesize that we will have auditory documentation of the presence of both harbor porpoises and baleen whales, with a low likelihood of detecting any North Atlantic right whales due to their endangered status under the Endangered Species Act and with the dominance of harbor porpoises and humpback whales (Delarue, et al., 2022; Tremblay, 2022).

This paper aims to examine the presence of baleen whales and harbor porpoises in the Penobscot Bay during the summer months of 2025. We hope to understand how potential factors of climate change and anthropogenic activity could be impacting the presence of these whales within this region. Currently, there is limited published data on marine mammal presence in the Gulf of Maine using PAM as the means of data collection. This leaves a significant knowledge gap surrounding marine mammal presence in the Gulf of Maine. By using PAM in high trafficked areas throughout the Gulf, such as Penobscot Bay, we can identify the time and location that different species are present. This data would help inform fishing, shipping and vessel routes, and further conservation practices.

II. Methods

Data Collection

A passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) device was deployed for 144 days, South of Hurricane Island in Penobscot Bay on May 8, 2025. Bathymetry near the deployment site reaches depths of approximately 100 m with a high-relief seafloor and many diverse bedrock outcrops. The passive acoustic recorder was bottom mounted without surface expression, anchored to the seafloor using a fixed weight (I-beam anchor) and equipped with a Vemco VR2AR release. Before deployment, the acoustic recording instruments were powered on, sealed, and attached to the mooring assembly—with the weight attached—and deployed over the side of the R/V Sunny at 44° 00.205 N, 68° 51.749 W (Figure 1) at a depth of approximately 55.5 meters. The passive acoustic recorder instruments used were a SoundTrap ST500STD (Ocean Instruments) and an F-POD (Chelonia) (Figure 2). To achieve high detectability, two PAM recorders were used: SoundTrap (records lower frequency calls) and F-POD (a click

detector that records information on echolocation clicks) (Todd et al, 2025). Once deployed, the SoundTrap device recorded continuously with a sampling rate of 24 kHz.

On September 27th, 2025, the mooring was retrieved using the Vemco acoustic release system. During recovery, the Vemco deck unit sent an acoustic signal with the release mechanism, triggering it to unscrew the bolt connecting the buoyant float to the seafloor weight, allowing the mooring to rise to the surface for retrieval. Once the buoy was spotted, it was brought back to shore on R/V Sunny.

Data Processing

SoundTrap data was offloaded and the sound files were run through the Low-Frequency Detection and Classification System (LFDCS). LFDCS is a software system created for automated detection and classification of low-frequency baleen whale vocalizations (Baumgartner & Mussoline, 2011). LFDCS scans sound files, analyzes frequency-modulated signals, and produces pitch tracks (Wilder et al, 2023). These pitch tracks trace changes in the frequency of a call over time on a spectrogram. A spectrogram is a graph that describes changes in frequency of a sound over time (Baumgartner & Mussoline, 2011). Once a pitch track is created, LFDCS compares attributes of the signal to a reference call library of species-specific call types to classify the pitch track as a certain species' vocalization (Wilder et al, 2023). Each marine mammal species produces relatively unique, identifiable vocalizations that can be used to distinguish them by sound alone.

Once the SoundTrap sound files were run through LFDCS, raw audio recorded sound files and LFDCS-generated selection tables of detections were loaded into Raven Pro (Version 1.6.5). Raven Pro is an acoustic software program that is commonly used to open, view, and analyze acoustic data. In Raven, LFDCS detections were manually reviewed to verify that each call had been correctly identified. Only data that are of higher quality detections, and that have been sub-sampled for validation, are reported in this paper.

The F-POD data was run through a KERNO-F classifier developed by Chelonia. Unlike the SoundTrap, the F-POD only collects information on the date and time, peak frequency, and amplitude; they do not record raw acoustic files (Todd et al. 2025). The FPOD recorder listens and logs these high-frequency clicks produced by porpoises that occur in a roughly 500m radius of the deployment location (Tremblay, 2022).

Data Analysis

Once the data was processed, hourly data for porpoise presence was extracted, and a histogram of the number of hours per day that porpoises were present (max 24 hours) was created using R Studio (Version 4.5.2). A map of the PAM mooring site was generated in ArcGIS Pro 3.6.

Figure 1: Topographic Map of Penobscot Bay (outlined in solid black line) with PAM mooring marked in yellow ($44^{\circ} 00.205\text{ N } 68^{\circ} 51.749\text{ W}$). Depth measured in meters (m). Data sourced from GEBCO Bathymetric Contours (NOAA NCEI Visualization) and U.S. Coastal Relief Models in ArcGIS.

Figure 2: Left: photo of SoundTrap ST500 instrument (credit: Ocean Instruments). Right: photo of SoundTrap after retrieval (credit: Marie Zahn).

III. Results

After processing the SoundTrap recorder sound files through the LFDCS, approximately 44,000 detections were obtained. Due to the large number of detections, LFDCS was run again separately for each species with an adjusted m-dist parameter in LFDCS to apply a more conservative detector to reduce false positive rates. Despite these additional runs of LFDCS with different m-dist values, no positive detections were found in Raven Pro. Therefore, LFDCS did not correctly identify the presence of humpback, minke, or North Atlantic right whales during the deployment. Due to time limitations, no further analysis was conducted for other large whale species (such as fin, sei, or blue whales).

After processing the full F-POD deployment period, porpoise echolocation clicks were detected on every day of the deployment (144 of 144 days). The mean summer Positive Detection Hours (PDH) was 18.92 hours per day (SD: 3 hr/day). Daily detection hours ranged from a minimum of 8 hours to a maximum of 24 hours. Monthly mean PDH varied across the deployment: 16.8 hours per day in May; 18.0 hours per day in June; 17.3 hours per day in July; 20.1 hours per day in August; and 22.2 hours per day in September. Given these values, there is an increasing trend in hourly detections of porpoises over the summer months.

Figure 3: Histogram of Porpoise Detection Hours Per Day in Penobscot Bay during June-September 2025. F-POD data revealed harbor porpoises were present every hour of the day in Penobscot Bay, Maine.

IV. Discussion

This study represents an important first step in providing baseline data for PAM of marine mammals in the Penobscot Bay. The Gulf of Maine is a known seasonal feeding ground for many baleen whale species and harbor porpoises (Davis et al., 2020). However, historical data recording marine mammal presence in the Penobscot Bay are extremely limited, thus making it difficult to interpret if the absence of baleen whales was novel or typical for this area. Although the Gulf of Maine is a feeding ground for baleen whales during the summer months, they are more concentrated in areas that are less constrained by surrounding geography. This could partially account for the potential absence of baleen whale detections, as Penobscot Bay has many islands and outcroppings that result in shallower bathymetry (Davis et al., 2020). This absence could also reflect the bay's shallow bathymetry or prey distribution during the study period being less favorable compared to other, more open areas of the Gulf of Maine. It could also relate to the changes in the ecological conditions where shifts in prey availability and oceanographic structure are increasingly realized as potential responses to climate change. As a result, previously present animals might be changing their interactions with these new environmental landscapes (Duarte et al., 2021).

In contrast, harbor porpoises were detected daily throughout the study with an increasing trend in hourly presence over the summer. While published diel and daily presence patterns in the Gulf of Maine are limited, harbor porpoises are known to concentrate in the northern Gulf of Maine and Bay of Fundy during the summer months before moving southward along the U.S. coast in the fall (Gaskin, 1984). Region-specific habitat-use patterns related to season, diel cycle, and tides have been observed elsewhere, but remain unknown for Penobscot Bay (Holdman et al., 2018). Higher hourly presence during the late summer months may reflect these factors; however, a longer-term PAM study is needed in this region to confirm seasonal trends. The consistent daily detections also align with historical trends that porpoises maintain regular activities, like foraging and navigating, in coastal areas, which makes them consistently detectable regardless of ambient background noise (Branstetter & Sills, 2022; Duarte et al., 2021). The contrast in detections highlights the differences in acoustic behaviors among various marine mammals. Specifically, harbor porpoises produce distinct high-frequency clicks, whereas baleen whales produce a much lower frequency which are more difficult to capture on PAM recorders in high-trafficked areas, such as Penobscot Bay, due to masking (Guan & Brookens, 2023). Masking is when underwater noise (of anthropogenic or natural origin) interferes with how marine mammals receive acoustic signals for communication, social interaction, foraging, or navigation (Erbe et al., 2016). An increase of 8–10 dB re 1 μ Pa at frequencies around 300 Hz in some oceans since the 1960s can be attributed to an increase in the number and size of vessels (Vagle, S., et al 2021). Understanding which marine mammals are present in the Penobscot Bay with current ambient noise levels is fundamental to understanding how increasing vessel noise and human presence will impact these marine mammals in the future. This data could also be used to develop a baseline soundscape for the region to determine human, ecological, and

geographical patterns and track changes over time. Baseline data could also be used for comparison against unusual manmade or geological events, such as offshore windmill development or seismic activity.

While this study offers an important initial assessment of baleen whale and porpoise presence in Penobscot Bay, monitoring over additional years and across broader spatial and temporal scales is essential to more fully capture the migration patterns of these marine species. Penobscot Bay is Maine's largest coastal inlet and contains numerous islands that may restrict sound propagation. Sound transmission can vary widely based on abiotic factors such as water depth, seafloor topography, substrate type, water properties, and sea surface conditions (Vagle et al., 2021). If this work is conducted again, the placement of the PAM mooring should be reevaluated. Given the relatively shallow bathymetry of the area and the tendency for large whales in the Gulf of Maine to be farther offshore, positioning the mooring farther from shore—where prey availability is higher, and the likelihood of encountering large whales increases—would likely improve detection rates. Investing in long-term PAM deployments in this region would help characterize interannual variability in species presence and migration patterns. Without previous years of data, it is impossible to determine whether the patterns detected in this study (e.g., seasonal presence, diel trends, call rates) are typical, increasing, or decreasing. The data collected here describe only presence and absence during the summer of 2025 and cannot yet reveal long-term trends.

Despite the lack of baleen whale detections during the short stretch of our study, future research could still detect whales within the Penobscot Bay which would encourage the use of regulations in the region. There are many human-caused threats to whales from human activity, including entanglement from fishing gear, collisions with ships, and noise pollution. Entanglement is one of the most immediately dangerous for whales, and with the Penobscot Bay's lobster industry we already have regulations on buoy lines, with rules dependent on the location of the line through the Atlantic Large Whale Take Reduction Team. (Fisheries, 2025; Piecuch & Lubofsky, 2019; "Right Whales and Entanglement in Fishing Gear"). An additional regulation we could propose in our region is reduced vessel speeds, called vessel slowdown. It would have two effects: the reduction of noise, and minimization risk of ship strikes. Vessel slowdown in shipping corridors has been shown to have a positive effect on expanding "the whales listening space" (Pine et al., 2018).

Figure 4: Visual illustration of the impact of vessel noise on a whale's listening space. (Pine et al., 2018)

Though the above graphic emphasizes the positive impact of vessel slowdown for whales, it also applies for other marine life including dolphin species, seals, and fish (Pine et al., 2018). Although vessel slowdowns increase the amount of time that a vessel remains in the area, evidence suggests that prolonged exposure to lower noise levels is less harmful than the brief exposure of higher noise levels associated with higher speeds (Findlay et al., 2023). The overall reduction of masking in the maritime ecosystem would also positively impact fish, who like marine mammals, struggle with the noise pollution generated by vessels and have been observed to avoid approaching vessels due to high noise levels (De Robertis & Handegard, 2013).

Currently, vessel slowdown rules apply to Atlantic shipping lanes to reduce the risk of ships striking endangered baleen whale species like the North Atlantic right whale in the Gulf of Maine and along the North American coast. These regulations are seasonal to follow the migratory trends of the North Atlantic right whale (NOAA Fisheries, 2025), however, additional research shows that not all individuals migrate, and a more proactive approach is needed (Davis et al., 2020). The suggested vessel speeds to reduce masking of 15 knots is only slightly higher than the suggested vessel speed to reduce ship strikes at 10 knots (Pine et al., 2018; NOAA Fisheries, 2025). Penobscot Bay could lead the way by reducing marine noise pollution and underwater masking, and this increased habitability could have ripple effects on the economy by encouraging further economic investment and development through increased tourism (Pan et al., 2018; "Sustainable tourism"). Vessel slowdown would increase the length of the ferry ride to and from Vinalhaven, general navigation around the islands, and, as critics within the fishing industry have argued, reduce productivity by increasing costs (Hotakainen, 2023). However, in the long term it would benefit the region because the decreased habitat disruption from masking

and noise pollution would promote a healthier ecosystem, and this could lead to broader investment in the eco-tourism industry (Li et al., 2023). Additionally, reduced vessel speeds can be less harmful to the climate by releasing as much as 24 percent less carbon emissions (Powell, 2025; Tran & Lam, 2022).

This study was limited, but the data collected strongly supports further research. The daily detection of porpoises in the Penobscot Bay along with the recordings of vessel traffic demonstrate that our industrialized region is teeming with life. Future research built upon our study could expand the understanding we have of life in and around the Penobscot Bay, and how we can better coexist with marine species, continue to develop our tourism industry, and still support our local fisheries. Like more PAM is needed in various locations around the Bay for longer stretches of time in order to detect baleen whale activity, regulations on vessel speeds would prevent masking both in our research and for marine life. This additional research combined with policy would also provide the needed baseline soundscape for monitoring environmental and ecological changes over time, which would assist with safeguarding the viability of the local resource economy.

V. Conclusion

Recording passive acoustic data in the Penobscot Bay is one way, along with visual observations, of tracking whale activity in this region, which so far has been understudied. As climate change continues to make alterations to our weather, water temperatures, and seasonal shifts in ocean currents, these factors influence the ecosystem, which in turn impacts whale species: where they feed, reproduce, and live. Collecting and analyzing PAM data is just one way to track the localized impacts of climate change but also determine how other human activities are influencing whale behavior and patterns, and how we can then be better ecological neighbors and environmental stewards. This specific research is limited to four summer months in 2025, but this provides a snapshot in time: by knowing which species live in the Penobscot Bay, but when and in what quantity, this study creates an argument for the need for future research. While no baleen whales were positively detected through this PAM study, porpoises were detected daily. This study was the first to begin developing baseline data of passive acoustic monitoring Penobscot Bay. We hope to build upon this data in the future as it is necessary for increased understanding of Penobscot Bay and marine mammal presence and detection—especially as the region continues to industrialize with offshore projects.

VI. Acknowledgements

This research would not have been possible without the support of our professor, Dr. Marie Zahn. We thank the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership and their staff for

allowing our class to spend a weekend using their facilities at Hurricane Island and assisting with our research. We would also like to thank Christopher Tremblay for his bioacoustic expertise and the hours he spent helping with data processing. Lastly, we would like to thank Nancy Arms (UMaine class of '84) who funded this research, making it possible; without their support, we would not have been able to take this unique field class at UMaine and grow as researchers and collaborators.

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The Relationship Between Sea Temperature and Porpoise Presence in Penobscot Bay

Cassandra Gardocki and Erin Grabe

1. Introduction

The Gulf of Maine is a rapidly changing environment. Due to several factors such as changes in water circulation in the Atlantic and atmospheric teleconnections from the Pacific, the temperatures in the Gulf of Maine have been gradually increasing from 1980-2015, with a dramatic increase from 2004-2013 (Pershing et al., 2015). In addition, the state of Maine is rapidly pursuing offshore wind farm development for a variety of economic purposes, including job creation and greater energy independence (Maine Department of Energy Resources, 2023). This project intends to mitigate the environmental impacts caused by fossil fuel emissions, but it gives little consideration to the effects on marine life beyond mentions of risk of entanglement and electro-magnetic field interference with hunting and foraging behaviors (Maine Department of Energy Resources, 2023). Environmental changes, ocean warming, and construction projects in the Gulf of Maine have broad impacts on the species that inhabit its waters.

The harbor porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) is found throughout the coastal waters of the northern hemisphere, with a sub-population in the northeastern United States (NOAA Fisheries, 2025). The most recent estimate of population size in the U.S. North Atlantic is 85,765, a number produced using aerial and sea vessel surveying techniques (Palka, 2023). Harbor porpoises generally hunt in the epipelagic and upper mesopelagic zones and have been recorded as having an average dive depth between 25 and 30 meters, though much deeper dives (greater than 300 meters) have been recorded (Westgate et al., 1995). NOAA Fisheries has identified two major threats to harbor porpoises: entanglement and ocean noise (NOAA, 2025), both risks identified by the State of Maine's Offshore Wind Roadmap (Maine Department of Energy Resources, 2023). There are numerous documented instances of wind turbine operation, construction, and maintenance associated with changes in porpoise behavior, up to and including relocation (Benhemma-Le Gall et al., 2021; Holdman et al., 2025). Previous research indicates that harbor porpoises do not have formal migration patterns, despite being a highly mobile species (NOAA, 2024). Satellite telemetry studies have indicated that the migration patterns of harbor porpoises are seasonal and gradual, often reflecting prey abundance in particular areas (Read & Westgate, 1997; Sveegaard et al., 2011). These gradual migration patterns tend to align with known concentrations of harbor porpoise prey species (Read & Westgate, 1997).

One study conducted in the Gulf of Maine found that while porpoise diets vary somewhat seasonally and geographically, it primarily consists of Atlantic herring (*Clupea harengus*), shallow-water cape hake (*Merluccius bilinearis*), and Atlantic cod (*Gadus mohua*) (Recchia & Read, 1988). These are generally about 10 to 25 cm in length, however they may also consume very small fish such as gobies (*Gobiidae*) (Kastelein et al., 2018). A 32-year study conducted in the Baltic Sea found that Atlantic herring and Atlantic cod were the primary food source for harbor porpoises, indicating relative consistency between populations of porpoises (Andreason et al., 2017). Environmental conditions influence the availability of these prey species. In other locales, temperature was positively correlated with herring populations and negatively correlated with cod populations (Akimova et al., 2016). Additionally, warming in the North Atlantic and the Gulf of Maine correlates to a decline in cod stock in the region (Pershing, et al., 2015). Warming conditions in the Gulf of Maine have coincided with hake populations shifting northward, leading to high concentration areas for both red and white hake in the Penobscot Bay region (LaFreniere et al., 2023). Ocean warming has created shifting patterns in the distribution and abundance of harbor porpoises' major prey species, which may influence porpoise activity in Penobscot Bay.

While Gulf of Maine porpoises gradually migrate to southern waters in the winter, there are recorded instances of individuals remaining in the Gulf year-round (Read & Westgate, 1997). A 10-site acoustic monitoring project conducted in the Gulf of Maine found that while porpoises were generally most active in the Gulf in the summer and fall, at one site (Mount Desert Rock), porpoise activity was at its highest during the winter (Holdman et al., 2025). This variation in behavior makes generalizing about the migratory patterns and behavior of harbor porpoises challenging, which speaks to a need for more research on regional sub-populations. In addition, deeper understanding of porpoise behavior, seasonal patterns, and relationships with the environment will help anticipate changes and impacts associated with rising sea temperatures and offshore energy developments.

In Penobscot Bay, normal seasonal fluctuations in ocean temperatures typically increase throughout the course of the summer from June to August (Gulf of Maine Research Institute, 2024). This study aims to determine if there is a relationship between ocean temperatures and the presence of harbor porpoises in Penobscot Bay. We hypothesize that harbor porpoise presence in Penobscot Bay will increase with water temperature throughout the summer months as indicated by previous research on other populations.

2. Methods

2.1 Data Collection

This study uses data from two sources: an acoustic recorder and ocean buoy. A mooring with an F-POD acoustic monitoring system was deployed on May 7th, 2025, in the Penobscot

Bay south of Vinalhaven (44.00°N, -68.86°W), where it remained until September 27th, 2025. This mooring was deployed and retrieved via Hurricane Island’s research vessel, M/V Sunny. The F-POD is particularly suited for picking up harbor porpoise vocalizations as they are relatively unique rates and frequencies (Tremblay, 2022). F-PODS are highly sensitive and maintain low false positive rates (Chelonia, n.d.). They use fully automated detection processes within a very fine temporal scale to record and store vocalizations (Chelonia, n.d.). Additionally, an ocean buoy site in the Penobscot Bay to the east of Vinalhaven (Figures 2 and 3) and north of Hurricane Island (Figure 3) (44.04°N, -68.89°W) was used to measure ocean temperature data at a depth averaging between 6 and 10 meters.

Figure 1: Photos of the Hurricane Island Ocean Buoy (left) (Wiley-Hicks, 2025) and the F-POD following retrieval (right) (Zahn, 2025).

2.2 Data Processing

Data from the ocean buoy was cleaned manually using excel to remove erroneous temperature recordings that possibly occurred during buoy changeovers. Outlier measurements were identified by significant one- or two-hour spikes in temperature readings. Data from the deployment date (May 7th) of the mooring with the F-POD recorder was also excluded from the final data. The deployment occurred in the early afternoon, and as a result, data from May 7th is partial.

All data was processed and all figures were generated using RStudio (version 2025.09.2) with RMarkdown using the packages *tidyverse* and *lubridate*. Both F-POD and Hurricane Island Buoy data were imported from excel and cleaned to reflect standard date and time formats. F-POD data was summarized to capture the total number of daily hours porpoise activity was recorded. Buoy data was averaged to capture the mean daily temperature over the deployment period. The F-POD summarized daily detections and buoy recorded daily average temperatures were then merged to produce a combined dataset for correlation and regression analysis. Generative AI (ChatGPT model 5.1) was used to optimize and troubleshoot errors in coding.

2.3 Statistical analysis

The cleaned datasets were reviewed to examine trends in daily porpoise activity and average daily ocean temperatures throughout the deployment period. This data was used to generate individual plots reflecting both daily average ocean temperature and porpoise activity (Figures 4 and 5). Using these cleaned datasets, a linear regression and Pearson correlation test was performed in RStudio to examine the relationship between ocean temperature and porpoise activity. The results of these tests were used to determine if there was a positive, negative, or no correlation between ocean temperature and porpoise activity, providing insight into whether temperature changes influence porpoise activity.

Penobscot Bay Research Site

Figure 2: Map showing the geographic area from which the data was collected. Three reference points are illustrated on the map, including the Maine town of Rockport, the Maine Island Vinalhaven, and the Penobscot Bay, all in blue text. Hurricane Island is labeled with a black arrow and blue text. The x axis reflects the longitude, while the y axis reflects the latitude. The ocean area is shaded in light blue, and land masses are shown in white.

Figure 3: Map showing the precise geographic location from which the data was collected. Hurricane Island and Vinalhaven are labeled in blue text. The F-POD deployment site and Hurricane Island Buoy are indicated by black text and red markers. The x axis reflects the longitude, while the y axis reflects the latitude. The ocean area is shaded in light blue, and land masses are shown in white.

3. Results

3.1 Ocean Temperature

Daily averages of near-surface ocean temperature data were calculated and graphed using a line graph. Review of ocean temperature data indicated gradually increasing temperatures throughout the study period (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Line graph depicting average daily water temperature in Penobscot Bay between May 8th, 2025, to September 27th, 2025. The x axis reflects the date, and the y axis reflects the average temperature in Celsius. Each point on the graph reflects the daily average calculated for that day. The line, in dark blue, shows gradually increasing ocean temperatures throughout the study period.

3.2 Porpoise Presence

Data recorded by the F-POD recorder reflecting hourly porpoise presence was summed to reflect a daily total number of detections. Porpoises were detected on all days throughout the deployment period, with increasing hourly detection rates from August 1st through September 27th.

Figure 5: Bar graph showing cumulative daily porpoise detections by the F-POD recorder. The x axis reflects the date, and the y axis reflects the positive porpoise detections per day. Each bar, in blue, represents the recorded total number of hours per day with recorded porpoise vocalizations.

3.3 Relationship Between Ocean Temperature and Porpoise Presence

Using the summed daily porpoise presence data and the averaged daily ocean temperature data, a Pearson correlation test was performed comparing daily detection rates and the corresponding day’s average temperature. The Pearson correlation test indicated a statistically significant, moderate positive correlation between daily average temperature and daily porpoise detection hours ($r=0.46, p < 0.001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.32, 0.58]$). The regression line shows an upward trend, which indicates that warmer days tended to correspond to greater porpoise activity (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Scatterplot showing the relationship between temperature and porpoise detections with a regression line showing a moderate positive correlation between water temperature and daily recorded porpoise presence in the Penobscot Bay. Points shown in light blue reflect the number of detection hours per day as they relate to average temperature. The red regression line with shaded confidence interval shows a moderate upward trend, indicating that porpoise presence generally increases with water temperature despite day-to-day variation.

4. Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to determine if a relationship exists between porpoise activity and ocean temperature in Penobscot Bay within the Gulf of Maine. Our hypothesis that there would be greater porpoise activity as water temperatures increase was supported by our findings. There was a statistically significant, moderate positive correlation between near-surface ocean temperatures and porpoise presence in the Penobscot Bay. This is consistent with research that focuses on various sub-populations of harbor porpoises (Holdman et al., 2025; Read & Westgate, 1997; Sveegaard et al., 2011).

Given the broader context of generalized porpoise behavior, one theory is that the correlation detected may correspond with other environmental factors not captured in this study. A key limitation of this study is the depth at which temperature recordings were collected (6-10 meters). Temperatures near the surface do not necessarily reflect the conditions and stability of

bottom temperatures. Solar radiation can play a significant role in warmer surface level temperatures, widening the difference between surface and deeper water temperatures. (Liu et al., 1994). Porpoises spend a majority of their time diving and foraging in deeper water, where temperature is lower and more stable (Westgate et al., 1995). Additionally, large concentrations of hake, which are bottom fish, have been recorded seasonally in the Penobscot Bay area where our research was conducted (LaFreniere et al., 2023). Further research in Penobscot Bay might include bottom temperatures and fish catch rates recorded by fishing vessels in the area to further strengthen and explain the relationships outlined in this study.

The present study adds to an existing body of work that demonstrates trends and correlations between sea temperatures and porpoise behavior. Updated research on the stomach contents of harbor porpoises in the Gulf of Maine may reveal changes in the diets of porpoises in response to depletion of fisheries, particularly cod, which has been severely overfished in the Gulf of Maine (Pershing et al., 2015). Recchia and Read's (1989) study provided insight into both the types and proportions of prey eaten by Gulf of Maine harbor porpoises, but the data is more than 30 years old, and the Gulf of Maine is changing rapidly. Warming waters have been documented as a risk factor for the relocation of Atlantic cod (Pershing et al., 2015), and hake populations are also relocating in response to warming conditions in the Gulf of Maine (LaFreniere et al., 2023). Deepening the understanding of marine mammal behavior and their relationships to environmental conditions is essential to understanding the impacts that further changes in the Gulf may have on these species.

Additional research and repeated attempts of this study design including more sites to capture a wider range of temperature data could provide more insight into the temperature preferences of harbor porpoises and how those temperature ranges correlate with prey concentrations in a given area. In their 10-site passive acoustic monitoring study, Holdman and colleagues (2025) did not detect any porpoise presence when water temperatures were 16 degrees Celsius or higher. The present study did not capture any temperature recordings greater than or equal to 16 degrees, but replications of this study may reveal a temperature range that porpoises are most suited to and provide further context on the correlations we detected.

5. Acknowledgements

We extend our sincerest gratitude to Nancy Arms, whose generous funding made this course and research possible. We also thank the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership, who provided staff, accommodations, food, transportation, instruction, and more on September 27th and 28th during and following the mooring retrieval. Special thanks to Nicholas Keeney, Adele Jordan, and Captain Albert, who came out with us to retrieve the mooring and allowed us to assist with other field research activities. We also thank professor Marie Zahn for providing us with an opportunity to conduct this research, in addition to her instruction,

leadership, and guidance on the field research trip. Marie also took extra time to provide feedback and assist us in learning how to use RStudio for data analysis. We thank our classmates, whose ideas, knowledge, and passion for marine science and research informed our approach to this project. Without the support from these people, this project would not have been possible.

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Rising Sea Levels in Bar Harbor, Maine

Ella Boxall

Introduction

Climate change is causing rising sea levels and increasing the frequency of storms. With this comes global consequences that impact ecosystems and people. Sea level rise is causing more frequent flooding, more severe erosion along the coast, damage to coastal and intertidal habitats, and salinization of water (both surface water and groundwater) (Nicholls, 2011). It is worth noting that population density is typically highest in coastal areas (Nicholls, 2011). This means that the consequences of sea level rise impact many people. A significant portion of Maine's population is concentrated along the coast. Nicholls (2011) discusses that a balance between adaptation and mitigation is necessary, as we must act both globally and locally.

When evaluating the impacts of sea level rise on communities, relative sea level rise is a more useful metric than the global sea level rise (Nicholls 2011). Relative (local) sea level rise evaluates global sea level rise, local changes in land elevation, and regional aspects of sea level rise. Relative sea level rise is driven by climate change, isostatic rebound, changes in ocean patterns, and more (Nicholls, 2011). Nicholls (2011) performed a literature review to evaluate relative sea level rise in several areas, but there is limited information available about relative sea level rise in Maine. Krueel (2016) analyzed the impacts of flooding in Boston, Massachusetts. She found that with one foot of sea level rise, tidal flooding in the city will occur about 75 times per year. This is very frequent and will have severe economic, ecological, and cultural consequences (Krueel 2016). She evaluated several datums and performed her analysis in three steps: flood frequency, mapping of flood-prone areas, and assessing vulnerability to flooding. The results revealed that it is necessary to take steps to reduce sea-level rise by decreasing greenhouse gas emissions, and that action is required on a local level to protect the city. This study aided visualization of sea level rise in Boston, and it highlighted the importance of having similar analyses done for Maine's coast.

Blankespoor and others (2014) evaluated similarly important concepts: they found that coastal wetlands are especially vulnerable to sea level rise. This is important for several reasons: wetlands are typically very productive and biodiverse ecosystems, and losing them will present losses in biodiversity for the planet as a whole; wetlands often act as carbon sinks, so the loss of wetlands due to climate change acts as a positive feedback loop; wetlands can accrete, which helps protect inland areas from flooding as sea levels rise (Blankespoor et al., 2014). For these reasons and more, wetlands are important to protect our planet, and rising sea levels are reducing their extent. Maine has many coastal wetlands, which are important ecologically, economically,

and culturally. It is important to know which wetland areas in Maine are at risk with different sea level rise scenarios so that the right steps are taken to prepare and protect them.

Despite increasing attention to coastal hazards, published research on Maine's future sea-level rise remains strikingly sparse. We must know more so we can best protect our ecosystems and communities. To enhance our knowledge and gain a more thorough understanding of sea level rise trends in Maine, I have projected sea level rise in Bar Harbor, Maine. My research objective is to determine how much the sea levels are likely to increase in Bar Harbor over the next 30 years using tidal station data. I will also determine whether or not king tides are increasing in frequency. This project defines king tides as any tide that is within 5% of the highest astronomical tide. Bar Harbor is near Acadia National Park, so having a more thorough knowledge of sea level rise will help us to protect areas that are culturally and ecologically important. Bar Harbor is quite densely populated compared to nearby areas in Maine, so focusing on Bar Harbor allows for a large impact on our ability to protect ecosystems and communities. Ultimately, the town of Bar Harbor will use this information to determine the height above sea level at which its dock should be built, but this data will also be useful for many other purposes. Sea level rise will have ecological, economic, and cultural impacts on the community. Bar Harbor and its nearby towns must know what to expect so they can prepare accordingly. This project will also help people better understand sea level rise, and the map I create will allow them to visualize the changes. I hypothesize that the sea level will increase and that with the increasing frequency of large storm events, king tides will become more frequent.

Methods

To evaluate changes in sea level in Maine, hourly tidal station data from Bar Harbor (Station 8413320) collected by NOAA (Figure 1) were used. The data is from 1947 to the present. MATLAB (version R2022B) was used to download and clean data from the tidal station and calculate moving averages on several timescales. These moving averages were plotted and the MATLAB curvefitter tool was used to find the statistical best fit. The best fit for the data was projected to 2055. A linear fit was also projected for a second estimate. These projections were compared to the Portland dataset projections to evaluate whether the results were in the correct range. To analyze the frequency of king tides, I am using `t_tides`, a MATLAB tool. This will allow me to determine the frequency of king tides and evaluate whether the frequency is changing. Figures 1 and 2 show where the tidal station is located in reference to Bar Harbor and Maine.

Figure 1: Tidal Station Location in Maine (NOAA Tides and Currents)

Figure 2: Tidal Station Location Within Bar Harbor (NOAA Tides and Currents)

Results

I found that sea levels have been rising in Bar Harbor since the data collection began in 1947, as shown in Figure 5. A third-degree polynomial provides the best fit to the data, although a linear model also performs well. I have used both to project the data to 2055, and the third-degree polynomial shows a larger increase in sea level rise.

Figure 3: Relative Sea Level Rise Projections for Bar Harbor, Maine. The yellow line shows yearly moving averages from 1947 to 2025. The blue line shows the degree three polynomial fit, with a projection from 2025 to 2055. The orange line shows the linear fit, which is also projected to 2055.

Figure 4: Sea Level Trends Over Time with linear fits across the same timescale used by the Maine Geological Survey (Sea Level Rise Ticker).

The rate of sea level rise was 2.33 mm per year historically (1947-2025), with a recent acceleration to 5.32 mm per year from 2000 to present. Sea levels have been rising in Bar Harbor since the data collection began in 1947, as shown in Figure 4. Sea level has already risen by about 16 centimeters, and is projected to increase by about 60 centimeters based on the degree 3 polynomial projection, or about 7.3 centimeters given the linear scenario, by 2055.

Discussion

This project has demonstrated that the sea level is actively rising in Bar Harbor, Maine. The projections for sea level rise differ slightly from the Maine Geological Survey projections of 2.45 mm per year historically and 4.56 mm per year since 2000 (Sea Level Rise Ticker). This indicates that it was necessary to update the values currently being used for Maine. The sea level

is increasing over time in Bar Harbor, Maine (Figure 3). Sea level rise is occurring at a growing rate (Figure 4). These are major changes, and they are statistically significant. Both figures show that immediate action by the Town is necessary.

One limitation of my study is that greenhouse gas emissions are not considered. This work only reviews hourly sea level data from the past and projects these trends into the future. For a more precise projection, it would be beneficial to examine greenhouse gas emissions and assess future sea level projections, considering this. It would also be helpful to look at larger-scale warming and cooling trends to create a more precise set of projections.

Conclusions and Future Work

Sea level rise is a growing concern for coastal communities, and it is necessary to know how it will impact each area. It is clear that Bar Harbor is experiencing sea level rise, and the rate of this rise is increasing. Future work will evaluate the tides. I will meet with the town of Bar Harbor to update them on my findings. Once I have determined the tidal constituents, I will project the frequency of king tides into the future. I will also generate maps of both sea level rise projections, with and without king tides, so that people can visualize the impact of sea level rise on their community.

Acknowledgements

I am extremely grateful to Tiago Carrilho Bilo for helping me with this project, Marie Zahn for guidance, Kaitlyn Mullen for suggesting the project and coordinating my meeting with the town of Bar Harbor, and Nancy Arms for funding the course and making the trip to Hurricane Island possible. I am also thankful to Peter Slovinski and Sean Birkel for providing historical context for the sea level peak in the 1970s.

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Phytoplankton Growth and Water Temperature in The Gulf of Maine

Becca Kreeger and Evie Runstrom

I. Introduction

The Gulf of Maine is a semi-enclosed sea within the Atlantic Ocean that is a large cold-water ecosystem. This ecosystem supports a large variety of marine life, ranging from a dense community of microorganisms to megafauna such as baleen whales. This diverse community is built upon the development of primary producers, with phytoplankton being a key portion of this community. While phytoplankton do not have a high biomass compared to other phytoplankton on the planet, they are responsible for almost half of the primary production on the planet. In the Gulf of Maine, phytoplankton are the backbone of a massive food web with their spring and fall blooms being a catalyst for many biological processes. This makes knowing and understanding the timing and composition of these blooms important for understanding how the rest of the community works.

The phytoplankton community in the Gulf of Maine has two primary blooms in the spring and fall with moderate amounts of production in the summer. The spring bloom has been found to be largely composed of diatoms, while the fall bloom is composed primarily of dinoflagellates. The dominant phytoplankton species in the Gulf of Maine are *Thalassiosira* spp., *Rhizosolenia hebetata semispina*, *Phaeoceros* spp., *Ceratium tripos*, and *Ceratium longipes*. The first three species listed are all diatoms that primarily exist in the spring bloom in April, while the last two are dinoflagellates that primarily exist during the fall bloom from June to October. These phytoplankton blooms are dependent on a large variety of factors, with a factor of interest being temperature. Due to changes in the climate from anthropogenically added carbon dioxide in our atmosphere, the temperature in many places is changing, including in the Gulf of Maine. These changes in temperature have affected the phytoplankton directly through their biology and indirectly by affecting things such as water column stratification.

This paper aims to explore how temperature affects the phytoplankton community in both their overall abundance and the diversity of species composed in the phytoplankton bloom. This information is vital for understanding how the phytoplankton population will shift over the coming years, and how those changes will affect the community going forward. This will be done through the temperature data collected from two different buoys. The Hurricane Island and Islesboro temperatures are provided by buoys used by Hurricane Island, and the Smith Cove temperature data was collected from a buoy maintained by the Maine Maritime Academy. The phytoplankton data provided by the Maine Maritime Academy Penobscot Bay plankton

monitoring program. The plankton data was collected using a FlowCam8000 which observes the species, class, biovolume, and abundance of plankton observed by the FlowCam.

With the changes in climate and the season that the data was taken in, we hypothesize that the temperature will have a positive effect on both the total abundance and the total biomass of the phytoplankton observed in this period. We also hypothesize that the abundance and biomass of dinoflagellates will be larger than diatoms due to the nearing fall bloom and because of their higher tolerance to heat.

II. Methods

Data collection

Phytoplankton abundance and biomass data were recorded across three sites in the Penobscot bay. Each sample constitutes a liter of water collected offshore. The samples were taken back to a lab, and the phytoplankton filtered out. Abundance and biomass data for various classifications of phytoplankton were provided through the Maine Maritime Academy Penobscot Bay plankton monitoring program.

Ocean temperature data was collected via Hurricane Island's Pen Bay Marine Data Project, which deploys two buoys, one offshore of Hurricane Island, and the other offshore of Islesboro. Additional temperature data from Smith Cove was recorded using Maine Maritime Academy's Smith Cove Ocean Observation Tool. Temperature data for each system is recorded every hour of every day.

Data Processing

Data was downloaded as excel spreadsheets, organized, sorted and graphed in order to determine and visualize trends in abundance and biomass of the plankton population between the three sites. For Abundance and Biomass, data was sorted by collection date. For visualization purposes, only the top 5 plankton species were graphed in the individual species charts. For the total abundance and biomass graphs, the data for every species was summed for every date, producing the total amount of plankton present in each sample.

Data on the temperature over time was pulled from the ocean buoy data. The temperature was recorded every hour of every day. For each day that a sample was collected, the full 24 hours of temperature recordings were averaged.

Figure 1: Map of the study area, via the Penobscot Bay Plankton Monitoring program website. The northernmost point is Smith Cove, the southernmost point is Hurricane Island, and the middle point is Islesboro.

Figure 2: Left: Top 5 species graphs by biomass; Top: Hurricane Island, Middle: Islesboro, Bottom: Smith Cove. Right: Top 5 species graphs by abundance, Top: Hurricane Island, Middle: Islesboro, Bottom: Smith Cove.

III. Results

16 species were considered for the above graphs. The other twenty categories in the dataset were excluded, either for being generic categories such as “8B: small particles <20um” or due to dubious data, namely *Pseudonitzschia* spp., which recorded several individual values as orders of magnitude larger than the sum total of every other category on the same day. Once the pool was finalized, the top 5 plankton species were determined by summing and averaging the abundance and biomass data for each plankton species at each of the three locations. In all cases,

the species with the largest sums also had the highest averages. The same five species were the most abundant and possessed the largest biomass across each location, with the only exception being *Eucampia* spp., which garnered the fifth largest abundance at Islesboro, beating out *Rhizosolenia* spp. However, *Rhizosolenia* spp. had larger abundances at both Hurricane Island and Smith Cove, as well as possessing the second-highest biomass at Islesboro, so it was included in the graph.

Figure 3: Top left; Total Abundance vs Total Biomass across all measured days at Hurricane Island. Top right: Total Abundance vs Total Biomass across all measured days at Smith Cove. Bottom left: Total Abundance vs Total Biomass across all measured days at Islesboro. Bottom right: Temperature variations over time for all three locations.

Each of the 36 categories of plankton were summed in Excel, and plotted by date of sample collection. Hurricane Island collected eight samples, Islesboro six, and Smith Cove three. Due to the limited number of samples at Smith Cove, it is more difficult to observe trends over time at that site. Also included in Figure 3 is a plot of temperature over time for each of the three locations, for the days that samples were collected.

Figure 4: Top: Hurricane Island Biomass and Temperature over Time. Bottom left: Islesboro Biomass and Temperature over Time. Bottom right: Smith Cove Biomass and Temperature over Time.

In the above graphs, plankton biomass over time is compared with the temperature over the course of sample collection dates. Due to variations in individual particle size, biomass is preferred to represent the total amount of plankton in the samples. The y axis scales for each graph are logarithmic, due to the large variance in the magnitude of the biomass. Additionally, the y-axis is identical on each of the three graphs, such that the values can be accurately referenced across them.

IV. Discussion

When observing the data that was collected, the trend that is most apparent is that temperature is positively correlated with both the total abundance and biomass of phytoplankton.

This is because an increase in temperature speeds up the photosynthetic process, which can lead to more growth and multiplication. This trend is normal to witness in the summer months as temperatures naturally rise in the Gulf of Maine during that time. This can be seen most clearly in the Islesboro graph, where days that were warmer led to a spike in the biomass of the phytoplankton in the following days. The data produced from Smith Cove does appear to display the opposite trend from what is discussed, but the Smith Cove data has far fewer points than both the Hurricane Island and Islesboro data sets. This leads the Smith Cove data set to be less reliable than the other two locations. More collections in Smith Cove would be needed to determine if this trend is present. While the positive trend of temperature and biomass of phytoplankton is natural in terms of the seasons, changing climate can shift how warm the temperature gets at varying points of the year. These changes can alter the patterns of phytoplankton blooms and change the pattern and length of these blooms with the most common trend observed being an increase in the biomass of phytoplankton. Due to the limited nature of this study, it cannot be determined if there are changes to the blooms in terms of climate change. More observation in the Gulf of Maine should be a strong priority to document any changes.

Observing the abundance of different species of plankton in the Gulf of Maine when compared to the study conducted in 2011, the phytoplankton community structure is much different than what was reported at the time. While some of the species that were reported in the top five of the previous study were observed by the FlowCam such as *Rhizosolenia* and *Ceratium Longipes*, many of the species listed in that study were not recorded at all. This difference may be a result of changes within the GoM, but it is important to note that the previous study reviewed the abundance of various phytoplankton species throughout the year while the research conducted within this project was only within a three-month period. Another thing to note about the species diversity is that all of the top species recorded were diatoms. This is interesting because not only are dinoflagellates typically more abundant within the fall bloom, but it has also been observed that dinoflagellates do better in warmer temperatures as well. Because of these observations, the results from this collection are contradictory to what was predicted. These results could be since most of the data collected was in the months of June and July, which means that the normal fall bloom window in the Gulf of Maine would not yet have happened. It is important to note that because of the limited scope of the project that was conducted, no conclusions can be drawn from these observations. A more in-depth and lengthy study should be conducted to fully understand the changes in phytoplankton communities in the GoM.

V. Conclusion

Studying the phytoplankton community and the changes it experiences due to climate change are very important for understanding the health and structure of the Gulf of Maine. Phytoplankton make up a significant portion of the primary producers in the GoM, making them

the backbone of most of the life we see in those waters. Based on the data received from this study, we expect to see an increase in phytoplankton when the water temperature is higher, since warmer temperatures accelerate the metabolic rate of the algae. This increase will hit a point when growth will no longer be supported, but it does not appear that that point has been hit within our studies. While it was expected that the community would be composed of more dinoflagellates, the top species recorded by biomass and abundance were diatoms.

The largest limitation on this research is the small sample size. All of the processed phytoplankton samples were taken in mid-July, so it will be difficult to get an accurate picture of the changes in biomass over time for phytoplankton species. The major blooms typically occur in the fall and spring, so surveying only in the summer misses both major blooms. Observing changes in the blooms as well as the overall population is critical for understanding changing dynamics in the Gulf of Maine. Therefore, the logical next step would be to process the additional samples collected at Hurricane Island in September and see how the data compares. The FlowCam should continue to run and collect samples throughout the year so that a yearlong understanding of the Gulf of Maine phytoplankton can be developed. This project has significant implications for the Gulf of Maine as an environment, since phytoplankton are the basis of the marine food web. Monitoring changes in phytoplankton species abundance could help predict changes in the environment before they fully take hold.

VI. Acknowledgements

This research was made possible by a generous donation by University of Maine Alum Nancy Arms. We would like to thank the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership for allowing us the use of their facilities during our weekend stay, and the valuable lessons we learned on board their research vessel. We would also like to thank our peer reviewers, Josie Aprea and Cassandra Gardocki, for their helpful feedback. Lastly, this research would not have been possible without the guidance and support of our instructor, Dr. Marie Zahn.

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Oysters and Other Shellfish Aquaculture: Site Selection in Maine

Kai Reed

Introduction

Background

Global demand for seafood is rising as the world's population continues to grow. However, wild-capture fisheries have been at their maximum sustainable yield (MSY) for many seasons, and they cannot expand further to meet the demand for a sustainable protein without damaging the fishery (FAO, 2022). Aquaculture is the fastest-growing food production industry and is essential to bridge the gap between the demand for sustainable protein and the current supply. This is increasingly relevant in the United States, where the second largest trade deficit, second only to petroleum products, is seafood. The United States imports 70–85 percent of its seafood, according to NOAA, and the demand for seafood is also rising. Seafood consumption rate per capita has increased from 16lbs in 1995 to 20.5 lbs in 2021 (Seafood Source, 2023).

Over 80% of the United States' current aquaculture farms are shellfish-based, with shrimp and salmon making up the rest (NOAA Fisheries, 2019). Shellfish aquaculture does not require external feeding, making it much cheaper and cleaner than offshore finfish aquaculture. Because they filter feed on whatever is in the water column, site selection is incredibly important to ensure they get enough nutrients while avoiding runoff or other contaminants. There is also the concern of boat navigation—both recreational and commercial—around the farms.

In Maine, the Damariscotta River Estuary produces over 50% of Maine's Eastern Oysters, *Crassostrea virginica* (Maine DMR, 2019). This location is just a sliver of Maine's 3,500 miles of coastline. What parameters make this region so profitable for aquaculture, and what other locations in the Gulf of Maine (GoM) compare?

About Oyster Farming

Oysters are bivalve organisms. They are sessile, meaning in the wild they spend their adult lives fixed in place and filter-feeding. Oysters filter feed on phytoplankton, detritus, and other organic materials in the water column. They are efficient filterers. A single oyster can filter through seven gallons of water per day. In aquaculture, oysters are typically cultivated from seed (juvenile oysters) produced in hatcheries. The most common cultivation method in Maine is "off-bottom" culture. This involves growing oysters in containers such as bags, cages, or trays suspended in the water column from floating rafts or fixed gear. Using these suspended gear

types allows the oysters access to more water flow, protects them from predation, and produces a more aesthetically pleasing shell.

Whether natural or farm-grown, the optimal temperature for oysters native to the Gulf of Maine is 10 °C – 25 °C, with colder water slowing growth. Even a few months of slower growth can hurt a farmer's operation. This is one reason why northern Maine coastal sites may not be chosen for oyster cultivation. Another factor to consider is Salinity. The majority of oysters grown in Maine are the eastern oyster, which needs a salinity range of 10ppt – 28ppt. Low salinity will cause stress in the oysters, which opens the door for diseases to take hold. Extended periods of time under 5ppt cause high mortality rates (DNR Maryland, n.d.).

Project Goals

The overall goal of this project is to identify suitable sites for shellfish aquaculture development in the Gulf of Maine by using satellite and buoy data. This project will analyze the environmental parameters that contribute to its productivity and investigate whether similar conditions exist in other regions along the Maine coast, using the Damariscotta River Estuary as a baseline. Specifically, the research objectives are:

1. To use buoy-derived data to identify key water quality parameters—SST, chlorophyll a, and SPM—in the Damariscotta River Estuary.
2. To apply the same methodology to assess and compare three other regions: the Hurricane Island area, the northern coast, and the southern coast.
3. To synthesize these findings to propose new, promising areas for sustainable shellfish aquaculture in Maine.

Note: Within the State of Maine, several factors limit the ability for any suitable location to develop an aquaculture farm. This paper will not approach the socio-political side of Maine's licensing processes and will operate on the assumption that these locations are open to farming. The licensing process can take several years, and its length deters many people and businesses from opening farms every year.

Methods

This study employed a comparative analysis of environmental parameters to assess the suitability of the Penobscot Bay site in the GoM for shellfish aquaculture. The Damariscotta River Estuary was used as a baseline for comparisons because of its highly productive shellfish aquaculture scene.

Potential Site Selection

Figure 1. A map of the Gulf of Maine pinpointing the location of the buoys used in each dataset with stars. From south to north: Damariscotta River, then Hurricane Island. See Table 1 for the latitude and longitudes of each buoy.

Site 1: Damariscotta River Estuary (Baseline Site): Data was obtained from Buoy E05, located near the mouth of the Damariscotta River. This site represents a known, high-productivity aquaculture region.

Site 2: Hurricane Island Area: Data was provided by the Maine Maritime Academy (MMA) monitoring program from Station F01 in Penobscot Bay.

***Site 3 & 4: Northern and Southern Coasts:** No data set could be found tracking water parameters in these locations. Only Sites 1 and 2 will be used in this study.

Table 1. Coordinates for each data buoy accessed.

	Common Name	Station Code	Owner	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)
Site 1	Damariscotta	E05	Maine Maritime Academy	43° 50	69° 34
Site 2	Pen Bay	F01	The University of Maine	44° 04	68° 89

Data Acquisition

To ensure a consistent comparison of the growing season, a fixed time frame from May 12th to October 21st was established. This time range was selected because this was the only range available from the Damariscotta buoy. The data from this baseline site was most recently updated in 2016.

The data from F01, The Pen Bay buoy, is from May 12th to October 21st of 2025. Because it is known that the Damariscotta has been highly productive, any site displaying the same characteristics in 2025 is considered promising for aquaculture development. The data sets collected were salinity, water temperature (at 2 meters below the surface), time, and chlorophyll concentration (From F01 only).

Data for the Damariscotta site were accessed from the University of Maine's buoy data portal (PhOG), while data for the Pen Bay buoy were accessed from the MMA HydroSphere platform. These datasets are all publicly available. See the citation page for links to all data sets.

For the Damariscotta and Pen Bay buoys, temperature and salinity could be compared, but because the chlorophyll a presence was only measured at Pen Bay, it will be discussed in terms of carrying capacity rather than a comparison. A final note on the data acquisition: Salinity data for Pen Bay was only recorded from mid-August to October. As such, it is not known how it compares to the salinities in the Damariscotta at the beginning of the summer season.

Results

Figure 2. Temperature and Salinity over time in the mouth of the Damariscotta River Estuary. The temperature rises and falls over the summer season, with its peak in mid-August. The salinity varies greatly, with its maximum in October at the end of the data set.

Figure 3. Temperature and Salinity over time in the Penobscot Bay. The temperature varies over the summer season, and peaks towards the end of August, where salinity increases slightly.

Figure 4. Chlorophyll concentrations in the Penobscot Bay location. The trendline displayed has a value of $y=0.0023x$.

Discussion

The comparative analysis between the Damariscotta River Estuary and Penobscot Bay reveals several key insights into site suitability for shellfish aquaculture. Temperature trends in both locations follow a similar seasonal pattern, which peaks in mid-to-late August, aligning with optimal growth conditions for *Crassostrea virginica* (10–25 °C).

Salinity profiles differ slightly between sites. The Damariscotta River exhibits greater oscillations of salinity, likely due to the tidal influence in the estuary, while Penobscot Bay maintains a more stable marine-dominated salinity trend. Although both salinity ranges fall within 31 - 33ppt, Penobscot Bay's stability may reduce stress and disease susceptibility compared to the more fluctuating estuarine conditions of Damariscotta. Chlorophyll concentrations, measured only at Penobscot Bay, indicate extremely stable phytoplankton populations throughout the season (Figure 4), suggesting a consistent food supply for filter-feeding shellfish. While direct comparison is limited due to missing chlorophyll data for Damariscotta, the observed levels in Penobscot Bay imply a strong carrying capacity for aquaculture.

Overall, environmental parameters at Penobscot Bay appear comparable to those at Damariscotta, with slight advantages in salinity stability and documented phytoplankton availability. These findings support the potential for expanding shellfish aquaculture operations in Penobscot Bay. This may be a more attractive location for a new oyster farmer, especially after the MSX outbreak in 2010 changed the restrictions on oysters coming in and out of the Damariscotta River (UMO Aquaculture Research Center, 2018).

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that Penobscot Bay exhibits environmental conditions similar to those of the highly productive Damariscotta River Estuary, including suitable temperature ranges and salinity levels within oyster tolerance limits. The presence of a consistent chlorophyll supply further suggests strong food availability for shellfish growth.

However, the analysis was constrained by incomplete datasets, particularly the absence of chlorophyll measurements at Damariscotta and limited salinity records for Penobscot Bay early in the season. Future research should incorporate comprehensive, year-round monitoring of temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, and tidal dynamics to refine site selection criteria. Deploying dedicated buoys and conducting in-person surveys would enhance data reliability and support informed aquaculture development in the Gulf of Maine. In the context of the ERS 321 class, this is as complete an analysis as possible, because there is neither time nor capability to deploy more buoys.

Based on current findings, Penobscot Bay emerges as a promising candidate for shellfish aquaculture expansion in Maine, complementing existing operations in the Damariscotta River and contributing to the state's growing aquaculture industry.

Acknowledgments

Thank you to Nancy Arms, UMaine class of '84, for her generous donation that funded the research conducted this semester in ERS321; Thank you to Marie Zahn for the continued support in the writing of this report; Finally, I would like to thank the staff of the Hurricane Island Center for Science and Leadership for their hospitality and for providing boating hours.

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